

Studies on the Effect of Some Ionic and Non-ionic Surfactants on the First Kind Polarographic Maxima of Cadmium-Iodide Complex

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The characteristic properties, viz., maximum suppression point (M.S.P.), specific suppression coefficient (S.S.C.) and critical micelle concentration (C.M.C.) of some ionic and non-ionic surface-active agents, viz., Manoxol-IB, Manoxol OT, Tergitol-7, Sodium lauryl sulphate, Lauryl pyridinium chloride, Cetyl pyridinium chloride, Lauryl pyridinium bromide, Tetradecyl pyridinium bromide, Cetyl pyridinium bromide, Cetyl dimethyl benzyl ammonium chloride, 2-ethoxy Ethanol, Ethyl diagol, Triton X-100, Gelatin and Amido black on the polarographic maxima of Cd-iodide complex, have been studied. Although the MSP, SSC and CMC values are not the same, but the same order of magnitude (10^{-3} % and 10^{-2} % or 10^{-4} M and 10^{-5} M) has been found to exist for various surfactants used. But for a few isolated cases, it is found that the amount of the detergent solution required to suppress maxima of similar sign is greater than those possessing dissimilar charges.

THE influence of maximum suppressors, viz., gelatin, agar, various dyes, glue, peptones, methyl cellulose, cationic, anionic and non-ionic soaps is well known in the polarographic investigations. In recent years new suppressors have been recommended by different workers. Amongst these mention may be made of the use of polyoxyethylene lauryl ether by Tamamushi and Yamanaka¹, dimethyl dodecyl amine oxide by Barradas and Kimmerle²⁻⁴, dodecyl ammonium and tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate by Kolthoff and Khalafalla⁵ and soaps (sulphonated phenyl, xylyl and tolyl stearic acids), dodecyl and dodecyl benzene sulphonates, dodecyl pyridinium bromide and isothiourea dodecyl ether hydrobromide by Malik and Haque⁶⁻⁸. But the surface active agents like alkyl aryl esters of sodium sulpho succinic acids, alkyl pyridinium salts and mono esters of polyethylene glycols have rarely been used as maxima suppressors in polarographic work.

In the present communication the authors have reported the results of polarographic measurements with cadmium ions in aqueous solutions of long chain surfactants of different polar head groups which exert a strong and insidious effect on the first kind maxima of Cd-iodide complex with particular reference to the characteristic properties of the surfactants and their role in the light of adsorption.

Experimental

Cadmium iodide and potassium iodide were of BDH Analaar grade. Anionic, non-ionic and cationic (TDPB and CDBAC) were of imported quality and the surfactants, viz., LPC, CPC, LPB, DBS, SLS were

obtained from Hico products as gift samples. Double distilled water was used for preparing solutions. Mercury for d.m.e. was distilled under vacuum.

Pyrex glassware was used in all the measurements. The dropping mercury electrode (d.m.e.) constituted of a standard capillary (E. H. Sargent & Co.). Temperature control at $20^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$ was accomplished by means of a relay and a Toluene regulator. A manual polarograph (Worsley Lane's) in conjunction with a Pye galvanometer was used for recording the potential and current respectively. Deoxygenation of the samples was done elaborately by a continuous flow of purified hydrogen⁹. Polarographic half cell was connected through an ammonium nitrate bridge to a saturated calomel electrode. Polarograms of the solutions were taken in the presence of varying amounts of surface-active agents until the maximum was completely suppressed.

Results

Height of mercury

column to tip of Capillary = 73.5 cm

Concentration of the

depolarizer = $25 \times 10^{-4} M$

Concentration of the

electrolyte = $2 \times 10^{-1} M$

Sensitivity of the

galvanometer = 2.5714×10^{-7} Amp/div.

Temperature of the bath = $20^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$.

Discussion

Heyrovsky and Vascautzanu¹⁰ found that the characteristic reproducible maxima which appeared on C-V curves with a d.m.e. arising at various cathodic potentials disappeared when the reduction potential of the reducible substance coincided with the potential at which the interfacial tension of the polarized mercury was maximum. The same statement was found to be true in the Cd(II) ions because cadmium ion in the presence of KCl does not give the first kind polarographic maxima due to the discharge potential in the range of electro capillary zero. But it is doubtful in the electro-reduction of capillary-active substances as cadmium iodide in very dilute iodide solution shows a maximum¹¹ which is difficult to suppress. The occurrence of the (positive) maximum is explained by the fact that the iodide ions are strongly capillary-active, and they shift the electro capillary zero to a more negative potential so that it no longer coincides with the discharge potential of the cadmium ions. The half-wave potential of the iodide-cadmium complex in 1M KI solution is shifted to -0.74 V vs. SCE and wave shows a pronounced maximum.

The three types of surfactants, anionic, cationic and non-ionic used in this communication are useful maximum suppressors for a number of metal and metal complex ions whose maxima could not be suppressed by the surfactants usually employed. For example, Kolthoff and Lingane¹² found that the first kind maxima of Cd(II) was a pronounced maximum which was difficult to suppress by ordinary surfactants. Therefore, with this opportunity these surfactants have a special advantage over the other suppressors of maxima of first kind of cadmium.

The polarographic characteristic properties viz., maximum suppression point¹³ (MSP), the suppressor concentration, precisely sufficient to eliminate the maximum under consideration, is obtained by trial method and computed by plotting values of i_m/i_a (ratio of diffusion current at maximum and when suppressed) vs. log concentration of the suppressor and extrapolated to complete suppression (where i_m/i_a is unity). Specific suppression coefficient¹⁴ (SSC), the suppressor concentration at which the maximum attains half of the value, is obtained by trial method. Critical micelle concentration¹⁵ (CMC), is defined and obtained by plotting i_m/i_a or $E_{1/2}$ or i_a (corrected for dilution) vs. log concentration of the suppressor and taking as that minimum concentration where the linear relationship first shows a sharp break or discontinuity. Their values are given in Table 1 (for anionic surfactants), Table 2 (for cationic surfactants) and Table 3 (for non-ionic surfactants).

Anionic Surfactants: It is evident from the Table 1 that the first kind maximum of Cd(II) is liable to suppression more efficiently by anionic surfactants. The values of MSP, SSC and CMC for surfactants Manoxol IB and Manoxol OT reveal

TABLE I—ANIONIC SURFACTANTS

Surface-active Agents	MSP	SSC	CMC
Manoxol-IB	$60 \times 10^{-2}\%$	$10 \times 10^{-2}\%$	$3.981 \times 10^{-2}\%$
Manoxol-OT	$5 \times 10^{-3}\%$	$2 \times 10^{-3}\%$	$2 \times 10^{-3}\%$
Targitol-7	$5 \times 10^{-4}M$	$2.5 \times 10^{-4}M$	$2.63 \times 10^{-4}M$
Sodium Lauryl sulphate	$6 \times 10^{-4}M$	$1.7 \times 10^{-4}M$	$1.7 \times 10^{-4}M$
Dodecyl Benzene sulphonate	$3 \times 10^{-2}\%$	$1.6 \times 10^{-2}\%$	$1.5 \times 10^{-2}\%$
Pepsin	$350 \times 10^{-2}\%$	$200 \times 10^{-2}\%$	$79.43 \times 10^{-2}\%$
XL-Anionic	$2.5 \times 10^{-2}\%$	$1 \times 10^{-2}\%$	$1 \times 10^{-2}\%$

some interesting features apart from the close examination of their structure formulae :

Due to the increase in chain length and with constant polar head group, the efficiency of the suppressor increases. Therefore, for surfactant having similar constitution, the suppressing power increases with molecular weight.

The superiority of Manoxol OT or dioctyl sodium salt of sulpho succinic acid, to other maximum suppressors for the cadmium iodide complex, whose pronounced maximum was earlier found to be difficultly suppressible, is thus established because maximum requires only a small quantity for suppression. Sodium lauryl sulphate and Tergitol-7 also prove to be efficient maximum suppressors. Furthermore, it may be seen from Table 1 that the amount of pepsin for suppressing the maximum (3.5%) is relatively larger than those required for other suppressors. Although the values of MSP ($3 \times 10^{-2}\%$ and $2.5 \times 10^{-2}\%$) for dodecyl benzene sulphonate¹⁶ and XL-anionic for the cadmium-iodide complex are small but seem to be less effective than manoxol OT. The values of SSC are found to be similar to those of CMC in the case of Manoxol OT, sodium lauryl sulphate and XL-anionic. This is due to the fact that the micelles formation starts at the point of half suppression.

On comparing the characteristic properties especially MSP values for anionic and cationic surfactants from Tables 1 and 2, it is found that the amount of the surfactant required to suppress the maxima of similar sign is greater than for those possessing dissimilar charges excepting a few cases. This characterisation of the surfactants gives further support to the adsorption theory. Therefore, for adsorption, larger concentration of the anionic surfactant for negative maxima will be needed than for the cationic one, since the adsorption characteristics are to be prevented by the similarity of the charges. Therefore, this shows that the Cd-iodide maximum is of negative polarity. The above fact is found to be true in the case of all the anionic surfactants used except Manoxol OT and supported by the fact that the resistance offered to the adsorption of the surfactant would be the least with the result that a relatively smaller amount of the surface-active agent should be used in bringing the desired effect. But the maximum of cadmium-iodide complex occurs just in the vicinity of electrocapillary zero, therefore, it is not definite to say that the maximum is of negative polarity as given by Malik and Haque⁸ but it can be positive as put forward by Winkel and Sievert¹⁷. This is also found to exist in the case of Manoxol OT which is used as anionic surfactant. Therefore the effectiveness of these anionic surfactants is found to be in the following order :

Manoxol OT > Dodecyl Benzene Sulphonate >
XL-anionic > Manoxol IB > Pepsin

Cationic Surfactants : Lauryl pyridinium bromide, Tetradecyl pyridinium bromide, Cetyl pyridinium bromide, Lauryl pyridinium chloride, Cetyl pyridinium chloride and Cetyldimethyl benzyl ammonium chloride were used as cationic detergents. These detergents were recrystallized thrice from acetone solutions. The behaviour of these cationic is rather peculiar. It is evident from Table 2 that the suppressive power of CPB is maximum and that of LPB

TABLE 2—CATIONIC SURFACTANTS

Surface-Active agents	MSP(%)	SSC(%)	CMC(%)
Lauryl pyridinium bromide	2.2×10^{-2}	5×10^{-3}	2×10^{-3}
Tetradecyl pyridinium bromide	2.2×10^{-2}	8×10^{-3}	5×10^{-3}
Cetyl pyridinium bromide	1.8×10^{-2}	6×10^{-3}	5.49×10^{-3}
Lauryl pyridinium chloride	1.38×10^{-1}	5×10^{-3}	2×10^{-3}
Cetyl pyridinium chloride	2.455×10^{-2}	10×10^{-3}	6.168×10^{-3}
Cetyl dimethyl benzyl Amm. chloride	2×10^{-2}	6×10^{-3}	6×10^{-3}

is least since former has larger chain length. In this way the capacity of suppression is directly proportional to the enhancing of chain length and polar head group behaves in the same way as already discussed. Therefore, this also supports that the cadmium iodide complex maximum has negative polarity as

given in the case of anionic surfactants by Malik and Haque (*loc. cit.*). The value of MSP for TDPB is analogous to that obtained in case of LPB.

On considering, LPC and CPC with identical polar heads and increasing chain length C_{12} - C_{16} , it is found that the suppressive power of the detergent decreases with chain length. Thus the capacity of suppression is inversely proportional to enhancing of chain length in the presence of chloride ions attached to the polar head. This supports that the cadmium-iodide complex maximum has positive polarity according to the idea of Winkel and Sievert (*loc. cit.*). But the above facts are similar to the statements given by Sharma and Srivastava¹⁸ in case of negative maxima of Ni(II) and positive maxima of Pb(II) respectively. CDBAC is less effective than CPB due to the presence of variety of substituents in the former compound.

Considering, LPC and LPB in which the chain length is constant and polar head group has the different halogen elements, the MSP values are quite different and increase as we pass from chloride to bromide but the SSC and CMC values are the same. This is due to the fact that the micelle formation in both the cases starts at the same concentration and the bromide ions are more adsorptive than chloride ions to the d.m.e. The SSC and CMC values are the same for CDBAC as found in the case of LPC and LPB. Owing to the general point of view that these cationic detergents behave as efficient maximum suppressors for negative maxima, therefore the statement, that the amount of the surfactant required to suppress maxima of similar sign is greater than for those possessing dissimilar charges, is found to be correct but it is not applicable frequently. These results are in conformity with those of Rusznak *et al.*¹⁹ Thus the efficiencies of the cationic surfactants are in the following order :

CPB > TDPB > LPB; LPC > CPC
and LPC > LPB.

Non-ionic Surfactants : The results obtained with the non-ionic surfactants are presented in Table 3. It is found that as the chain length increases from 2-ethoxy ethanol to ethyl diagol the MSP value enhances and the concentration of micelle formation decreases but the amounts for suppression are much greater to other suppressors, since the said detergents have very low molecular weights. Considering,

TABLE 3—NON-IONIC SURFACTANTS

Surface-active Agents	MSP(%)	SSC(%)	CMC(%)
2 Ethoxy - Ethanol	45.71	15.00	15.00
Ethyl diagol	56.23	14.50	12.88
Triton X-100	3×10^{-3}	1.33×10^{-3}	1.33×10^{-3}
Gelatin	10×10^{-3}	2.34×10^{-3}	2.34×10^{-3}
Amido Black	4.365×10^{-3}	1.55×10^{-3}	0.9772×10^{-3}

Triton X-100, gelatin and amido black as maximum suppressors, the values of MSP, SSC and CMC are not the same but the same order of magnitude (10^{-3} %) has been found to exist for Cd iodide complex maximum. The suppressive powers of these three non-ionic detergents are more than all other anionic and cationic surfactants used for this particular metal ion complex. On comparing the MSP values of gelatin and Triton X-100, it is found that the latter has a stronger influence on the electrode reaction than gelatin, because Triton X-100 consists of smaller, more similar molecules of nearly same molecular weight as stated by Schmid and Reilley²⁰. But in the case of gelatin there is high molecular weight and a broader distribution of size and structure. Therefore, the structure of Triton X-100 may be more closely packed than those of gelatin. Thus, this fact may exhibit stronger adsorption characteristics. The suppressive powers of these non-ionic surfactants are in the following order :

Triton X-100 > Amido Black > Gelatin > 2-Ethoxy ethanol > Ethyl diagol.

As we have stated that the cationic surfactants generally suppress the negative maxima and the anionic agents eliminate the positive ones but these non-ionic surfactants have an extra advantage because they can suppress both the positive and the negative maxima. Moreover, a much smaller amount of the reagent is required for suppression as compared to the anionic and cationic surfactants (Tables 1, 2).

The characteristic properties for all the ionic and non-ionic detergents are depicted in the representative graphs (Figs. 1, 2, & 3). The values of CMC for each suppressor is determined by two graphs plotted between i_m/i_d vs. $\log C$ and $E_{1/2}$ vs. $\log C$ and are found to be identical. Although the values of MSP, SSC and CMC are not the same, but the same order of magnitude has been found to exist for anionic, cationic and non-ionic detergents used.

Fig. 1. Anionic surfactants—Pepsin

○ i_m/i_d vs. $\log C$
 △ $-E_{1/2}$ vs. $\log C$.

Fig. 2. Cationic surfactants—CPB

○ i_m/i_d vs. $\log C$
 △ $E_{1/2}$ vs. $\log C$.

Fig. 3. Non-ionic surfactants—2 ethoxy ethanol.

○ i_m/i_d vs. $\log C$
 △ $E_{1/2}$ vs. $\log C$.

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